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Michael Stiebe

Special Issue

Electric and Hybrid Electric Aircraft Propulsion Systems

Edited by

Prof. Dr. Kaushik Rajashekara and Dr. Hao Huang

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Accelerating Sustainable Electric General Aviation with Fast-Charging Networks at Regional Airfields: Opportunities and Challenges

Michael Stiebe ^{1,2}

¹ Competence Center for Mobility, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (HSLU), Rösslimatte 48, 6002 Lucerne, Switzerland; michael.stiebe@hslu.ch or michael.stiebe@unibas.ch; Tel.: +41-41-349-36-24

² Faculty of Business and Economics, University of Basel (UniBas), 4052 Basel, Switzerland

Abstract: Electric aviation (eViation) is a promising pathway for sustainability in General Aviation (GA), particularly pilot training. However, challenges such as limited aircraft models, low battery endurance, long charging times, and inadequate charging infrastructure at most airfields—exacerbated by a lack of charging standardization—hinder eViation adoption. This study explores key factors influencing the feasibility of establishing a fast-charging network for electric airplanes in Switzerland, addressing infra-structural, technological, and policy barriers, as well as stakeholder concerns. Using a sequential mixed-methods approach, we analyzed 7000+ electric flight records and conducted an online stakeholder survey (n = 44) and 21 qualitative expert interviews. The findings reveal strong interest in eViation but highlight critical gaps, including sparse charging infrastructure and the need for standardization. Stakeholders emphasize transitioning to the Combined Charging System (CCS), integrating renewable energy, and implementing policy measures like subsidies and operational privileges. However, a chicken-and-egg dilemma persists: limited infrastructure hampers aircraft adoption, yet investment is difficult without widespread use. Lessons from the automotive EV transition highlight the need for strategic infrastructure expansion and coordinated policies. Remarkably, stakeholders prioritize network density over charging speed. This study identifies key barriers and opportunities for eViation adoption, providing actionable recommendations for the sustainable GA transition.

Keywords: electric airplanes; general aviation; fast-charging network; sustainability; light aviation; sustainable general aviation; electric aviation; Switzerland

Academic Editors: Kaushik Rajashekara and Hao Huang

Received: 16 January 2025

Revised: 17 February 2025

Accepted: 20 February 2025

Published: 21 February 2025

Citation: Stiebe, M. Accelerating Sustainable Electric General Aviation with Fast-Charging Networks at Regional Airfields: Opportunities and Challenges. *World Electr. Veh. J.* **2025**, *16*, 118. <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj16030118>

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1. Introduction

Aviation is increasingly highlighted for its environmental impacts, particularly its contributions to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Despite accounting for only 1.5% to 3.5% of global CO₂-equivalent (CO_{2e}) emissions [1,2], the aviation sector remains highly energy-intensive and reliant on fossil fuels, prompting growing pressure from policymakers and society to accelerate decarbonization. Although commercial aviation has implemented initiatives—such as investing in Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs) and mitigating noise—there is comparatively less attention on the civil aviation sector of General Aviation (GA) which has been widely flying under the sustainability radar until a few years ago [3].

According to the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), GA is defined as “all civil aviation operations other than scheduled air services and non-scheduled air

transport operations for remuneration or hire” [4]. GA, often confused with “aviation in general”, frequently sparks mental images of recreational flying activities on small single-engine piston airplanes at small (rural) airfields. While this only applies to a small share of GA, approximately three-quarters of the 40 million annual GA flight hours worldwide are generated by activities such as pilot training, business aviation, agriculture including crop spraying, emergency medical services, and civil search and rescue, among others [4,5].

Although GA represents a broad set of activities, it accounts for only about 4% of total aviation fuel consumption—translating to approximately 1–2% of the entire aviation sector’s CO_{2e} emissions [6–8]. Its smaller share of overall emissions has until recently limited the urgency surrounding GA’s environmental impact. Aside from the broad array of included activities, this paper primarily focuses on private pilot training and light aviation, particularly with fixed-wing aircraft.

Along with a drastically worsening public image, public aversion, and even increasing climate activist attacks on private planes over recent years, GA is facing distinct sustainability challenges such as demographic change, shrinking numbers of private pilot license holders (see, e.g., Figure 1), increasing costs, local restrictions, airfield closures, outdated and fuel-inefficient piston-engine airplane fleets (the average GA aircraft is now nearly 50 years old), widespread dependency on leaded aviation gasoline (AVGAS100LL) which raises concerns over both environmental harm and public health, and increasing noise sensitivity of near-airfield residents in Europe, as well as a limited range of feasible alternatives and means to facilitate a sustainability transition [3,9–13]. While the European Union had originally decided in 2022 [14] that the production of AVGAS with tetraethyllead additives was supposed to be banned in Europe by 2025, the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) recently granted extension permits to companies for further production of AVGAS 100LL up until 2032 [15].

Figure 1. Development of pilot licenses in Switzerland from 1990 to 2023. Based on FOCA [16].

For instance, the aforementioned SAF, designed as a drop-in replacement for Jet-A1 fuel and being scaled up at a fast pace in the commercial aviation sector, is no practical alternative for the majority of GA aircraft with piston engines predominantly running on AVGAS.

Thus, one promising avenue for decarbonizing GA is electric aviation (henceforth eViation). Advancements in battery technology and powertrain efficiency have enabled fully electric light aircraft, most notably the Pipistrel Velis Electro (see Figure 2), which became the first electrically powered airplane to achieve European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) type certification (*EASA.A.573 TCDS*) in the summer of 2020 [17]. The Pipistrel Velis Electro, the first fully certified electric aircraft, represents a significant step

in the decarbonization of GA. With a useful load of 172 kg, a cruise speed of 90 KCAS (167 km/h), and a maximum endurance of approximately 50 min plus VFR reserve of 30 min, the aircraft is particularly suited for flight training applications. It features a 57.6 kW peak power output electric motor and two lithium-ion battery packs (Pipistrel PB345V124E-L) with a total energy capacity of 24.8 kWh. Each battery pack weighs ~70 kg, bringing the total battery weight to ~140 kg. Its rate of climb of approximately 3.4 m/s (670 ft/min) and a fixed tricycle landing gear configuration further contribute to its suitability as a trainer aircraft. While its endurance is currently limited due to battery constraints, advancements in battery technology and charging infrastructure could further enhance its operational viability. For more technical details of the current most used electric aircraft, please refer to Table A1 in the Appendix A.

Figure 2. Pipistrel Velis Electro at a rural airfield in Central Switzerland. Source: Author.

Electric aircraft can greatly reduce noise and local air pollution while slashing carbon emissions, especially if powered by renewable energy sources [18]. Bearing in mind that there are frequent concerns in the GA community regarding the environmental impact of battery production [9], it is important to consider the results in Dubois [19], who determined through his LCA that, under ideal conditions, a Pipistrel Velis Electro's battery production emissions are offset after just 38 flight hours compared to the use of a frequently used (especially in pilot training) Cessna 150.

Additionally, eViation is particularly suitable for and increasingly popular in flight training activities, where short takeoff–land cycles and local flights dominate operations [3]. Switzerland, for instance, has emerged as an enthusiastic early adopter and developer of electric aircraft (e.g., *smartflyer*, ETH Zurich's *e-Sling*, or H55), spurred by local policies favoring clean energy, the availability of innovative infrastructure projects, and a heightened public focus on sustainability [9].

In the context of flight training, a study from 2022 calculated the potential use phase emissions savings to reach up to 1.5 tCO_{2e} for the standard PPL(A) syllabus, under the condition that all suitable lessons (i.e., flights < 50 min) in the syllabus are substituted using the Pipistrel Velis Electro, compared to full PPL training conducted on a Piper Archer (PA28).

Although a few niche products and few prototypes exist in the battery electric aircraft segment, the current electric GA landscape is clearly dominated by Pipistrel Aircraft. In comparison to the global GA aircraft fleet, the electric aircraft fleet, mainly comprising *Pipistrel Velis Electro* (and its predecessor *Pipistrel Alpha Electro*), accounts for only a very

small fraction at the moment, which is less than 0.01%. On 7 March 2024, Pipistrel announced that the company manufactured its 100th Velis Electro airplane which went into service in Germany [20,21]. As of December 2024, the concentration of Pipistrel Velis Electro aircraft is the highest in Europe, with France leading the ranking with 35 registered Pipistrel Velis Electro aircraft as of December 2024 [22], followed by the United Kingdom with 12 [23] and Switzerland with 12 registered Velic Electro aircraft [24].

Despite these positive developments, a number of significant barriers limit the widespread adoption of electric aircraft. The Pipistrel Velis Electro still has restricted battery capacity, allowing for only 45–60 min of usable flight time, thus not allowing for full private pilot license (PPL) syllabus coverage (especially cross-country flights with mandatory landings at external airfields). This means that while electric aircraft can and are already being used for large fractions of the training syllabus, complementary training flights with conventional single-piston-engine planes are required. Ideally, these flights are conducted using the Pipistrel Virus, which is a similar airframe with comparable aerodynamic properties and handling yet powered by a gasoline-fueled Rotax engine. However, in many flight school fleets (particularly smaller flight schools), this is not the case. Additionally, charging times remain comparatively long—up to 90 min—using the currently available GB/T standard charger at 22 kW power, which constrains training schedules and operational flexibility. The latter applies especially to smaller flight schools that only have one electric aircraft in their fleet. The currently utilized GB/T charging standard in Pipistrel planes can be seen as a major inhibitor for advancing universal eViation charging infrastructure since other aircraft manufacturers (e.g., Diamond Aircraft with their eDA40 project, or H55 with their B23 project) are signaling to opt for the Combined Charging System (CCS) which has also emerged as the prevailing charging standard in the automotive sector in Europe. The standardization of charging in the eViation sector has been a lengthy process, as demonstrated in the case of the still not finalized SAE AS6968 standard (“Connection Set of Conductive Charging for Light Electric Aircraft”) authored by the *Ae-7d Aircraft Energy Storage And Charging Committee* [25]. Regardless, Pipistrel has also recently signaled to also enable a transition towards CCS and will soon offer GB/T—CCS adapters to enable more flexible use of charging solutions as there are currently only OEM 22kW chargers and the EASA-certified alternative from Eaton, i.e., SKYCHARGE [26,27]. Furthermore, it is expected that Pipistrel will increase the permitted charging speed two-fold, allowing for a potential halving of charging time.

Furthermore, charging infrastructure at regional and rural airfields, where large volumes of PPL training flights are generated, is often insufficient or absent, and this is perceived by the GA community as a leading obstacle to eViation adoption [9]. However, survey-based studies in Europe and North America confirm that stakeholders perceive eViation as an appealing, environmentally responsible alternative to legacy piston-engine aircraft, especially for pilot training [9,19,28,29].

Drawing on key lessons from the electromobility transition in the automotive sector, we hypothesize that the development of a standardized and strategic fast-charging network, ideally multimodal (airplanes and EVs using the same charger), along with smart policy measures and incentives could significantly increase the adoption of electric planes in flight training and private aviation. We imagine that especially smaller rural and regional airfields, often subject to little to no fences or inaccessibility via private car, could be suitable to establish such a multimodal charging network for cars and planes using the same chargers.

Examples like the Norwegian EV policy and subsidy mix showed throughout the last years that typical barriers to the adoption of EVs, foremost low range (and associated *range anxiety*) and higher vehicle purchasing prices, could be overcome by using a mix of

policy measures, convenient incentives (e.g., toll road payment exemptions), privileges (e.g., permission to use bus/taxi lanes), subsidies and the development of an advanced public fast-charging infrastructure [30].

Firstly, low battery capacity and endurance may be symptomatic of a technology that is still in its early stages and at the beginning of the innovation adoption cycle; such obstacles were also prominent a few years ago in the automotive transition towards electromobility [19,31]. While the adoption of EVs is critical to transitioning toward sustainable transportation and one of the *grand narratives* of sustainable mobility [32], numerous barriers hinder widespread adoption, including limited driving range and slow charging times, high upfront costs, insufficient charging infrastructure, and lack of consumer awareness and trust in EV performance. For example, range anxiety and concerns about charging availability are often significant deterrents to potential buyers [33]. Financial barriers such as the high initial cost of EVs and uncertainties regarding their long-term economic benefits intensify these challenges [34]. Behavioral factors, including resistance to new technologies and lack of consumer knowledge about EVs, further slow adoption rates [35].

To overcome these barriers, targeted interventions and policies are crucial. Expanding charging infrastructure and reducing the high upfront cost of EVs through subsidies or tax incentives are proven strategies to encourage adoption [30,36,37]. Saether [38] concludes and emphasizes in his review study drawing on panel data from 32 European countries from 2009 to 2019 that expansion of public fast-charging infrastructure significantly increases EV market share and that policy packages going along with this are more efficient than single EV promotion policies.

Drawing on these lessons from the automotive EV transition, we attempt to build our research on electric charging networks and the adoption of electric planes and integrate the research later with the discussion of our empirical results.

1.1. Purpose and Scope of the Study

While this study addresses the transition towards sustainable GA, it should be noted that there is currently neither a universal definition of sustainable aviation nor sustainable GA. In the late 1990s, debates about sustainable aviation arose after the publication of the IPCC Special Report on the climate change impacts of aviation [39,40]. The topic has since attracted increasing attention from stakeholders and brought about several definitions. Based on various definitional approaches [3,41–43] for sustainable aviation, we define sustainable GA in an adapted fashion:

“Sustainable GA is a transition pathway that integrates social, technological, economic, and political measures, alongside research efforts, to holistically transform GA operations. This transformation ensures that GA activities—defined as the operation of heavier-than-air aircraft for civil aviation outside of scheduled air services and non-scheduled air transport for remuneration or hire—do not accelerate global warming, degrade the biosphere, or impede global economic prosperity and human connectivity”.

This mixed-methods research—combining data-driven electric flight record analysis, a quantitative stakeholder survey, and semi-structured qualitative interviews—aims to explore the key factors influencing the feasibility of establishing a Switzerland-wide multimodal fast-charging network for electric GA airplanes at Swiss airfields. It thereby addresses one of the primary barriers—limited infrastructure [9,19]—currently impeding eViation growth.

Specifically, we (1) statistically analyze more than 7000 Swiss electric flight records to gauge current usage patterns, (2) integrate GA stakeholder perspectives gathered via a survey and semi-structured in-depth interviews to identify key infrastructural, technical, and policy gaps, and (3) discuss pathways to overcome these challenges, drawing on

parallels from the EV sector and international best practices. By synthesizing these data, this study aims to inform policymakers, airfield managers, flight school operators, and private investors, offering a strategic framework to expedite the shift toward electric GA. The results can also serve as a blueprint for other countries exploring similar clean aviation initiatives.

1.2. Principal Conclusions

In brief, our findings underline that eViation in the pilot training and recreational flying sectors is currently facing a typical “chicken and egg dilemma” as known from the EV transition in the automotive sector—without sufficient charging infrastructure, there will be no widespread adoption of electric vehicles/planes, and vice versa. An important finding is that many GA stakeholders do not perceive current charging times as a major obstacle but rather the low density of charging infrastructure at airfields.

Thus, based on combined results from the literature and market analysis, qualitative expert interviews, as well as GA stakeholder perceptions obtained through a quantitative survey, our study concludes that standardizing and expanding non-proprietary charging infrastructure—particularly through fast-charging solutions—could significantly enhance the operational viability of electric aircraft in GA, particularly pilot training. When coupled with targeted policy measures (e.g., subsidies, usage privileges and incentives such as free or discounted landing fees, grid-capacity investments, and stakeholder coordination), these developments can help overcome current technological and logistical barriers while the technology improves and new airplane models with faster charging speeds and longer battery endurance penetrate the market.

As a result, this study strongly indicates that improving infrastructure and incentives can catalyze more sustainable pilot training and recreational flying, accelerate the adoption of eViation technologies, and significantly contribute to the sustainability transition of GA through a reduction in noise as well as carbon and atmospheric pollutant emissions from leaded AVGAS.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 details the mixed-methods design, including flight record analysis, qualitative interviews, and the online survey. Section 3 presents empirical findings, focusing on existing charging initiatives in Europe, statistics on electric flight usage in Switzerland, and survey/interview insights. Section 4 discusses the implications, placing them in the broader context of sustainable mobility and policy development. Finally, Section 5 concludes with recommendations and future research directions aimed at accelerating eViation adoption in both Swiss GA and beyond.

2. Materials and Methods

This study employs a sequential mixed-methods approach to explore key factors influencing the feasibility of establishing a fast-charging network for electric aircraft in Switzerland. Rather than conducting a full feasibility analysis, this study identifies and assesses infrastructural, technological, and policy barriers that impact the development and adoption of such a network.

After the market and literature (gray and academic literature) analysis, our study methodology integrates three key components: (1) quantitative analysis of electric flight records, (2) a trilingual nationwide GA stakeholder survey, and (3) semi-structured qualitative interviews. This triangulation of data sources allows for a comprehensive understanding of both operational trends and stakeholder perspectives, improving data reliability and validity. An overview of the study’s research flow is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Research flow.

2.1. Research Design

The study follows a sequential explanatory design, where quantitative data (flight records, survey responses) provide an overarching understanding of eViation adoption,

while qualitative insights (since the quantitative survey also contained a few open-ended questions, we also had qualitative hints and insights through the survey), such as semi-structured interviews, offer deeper explanations of observed trends. This approach ensures a holistic assessment of infrastructure needs, technological barriers, and policy implications. By structuring the study sequentially, we can first derive patterns from empirical data and then validate and explain them through stakeholder perspectives.

2.2. Electric Flight Records

Flight records were obtained through collaboration with AlpinAirPlanes GmbH (1663 Epagny, Switzerland), which operates Switzerland’s only structured eViation network. The dataset includes 7168 electric flights recorded between 16 February 2021, and 21 October 2024, covering more than 3000 flight hours across 14 electric aircraft. As of January 2025, 12 Pipistrel Velis Electro aircraft remain active in Switzerland. Data were collected directly from onboard flight logging systems. Each flight log included time stamps, aircraft identification, airfield location codes, and operational metrics. The dataset includes the following:

- Date of Flight;
- Aircraft (Registration: HB-. . .);
- Operator (Flight School/Club);
- Take-Off and Landing Airfields (ICAO Codes);
- Number of Landings;
- Off-Block and On-Block Times;
- Stick-Off and Stick-On Times;
- Total Airborne Time (Minutes);
- Total Block Time (Minutes).

Data were checked for inconsistencies, duplicates, and erroneous entries. Descriptive statistical analysis was performed to identify flight patterns (e.g., outside landings, frequency relationships between different airfields), infrastructure dependencies, seasonal variations, and correlations between charging infrastructure and aircraft utilization. An excerpt of the used data (screenshot of spreadsheet) can be seen in Figure 4. To maintain confidentiality, this study does not disclose individual flight school names or aircraft registrations.

1	Date	Aircraft	Pilot	Takeoff	Landing	Num ldg	Off block	On block	Stick off	Stick on	Total airborne (min)	Total block (min)	Hourmeter (min)	Notes
1952	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	4	13:17:00	14:02:00	13:24:00	13:58:00	34	45	64.42	
1953	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	13:14:00	13:46:00	13:19:00	13:41:00	22	32	63.67	
1954	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	5	13:07:00	14:12:00	13:15:00	14:09:00	54	65	63.13	
1955	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	12:34:00	12:58:00	12:40:00	12:54:00	14	24	62.05	
1956	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	10:49:00	11:32:00	11:01:00	11:28:00	27	43	61.65	
1957	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	09:53:00	10:02:00	09:54:00	09:58:00	4	9	60.93	
1958	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	2	09:32:00	10:04:00	09:41:00	09:59:00	18	32	60.78	
1959	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	09:14:00	09:52:00	09:23:00	09:49:00	26	38	60.25	
1960	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	2	07:37:00	08:20:00	07:42:00	08:17:00	35	43	59.62	
1961	26.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	06:10:00	07:05:00	06:15:00	06:55:00	40	55	358.9	
1962	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	16:39:00	16:47:00	16:40:00	16:44:00	4	8	73.25	
1963	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	16:28:00	16:36:00	16:29:00	16:33:00	4	8	73.12	
1964	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	16:16:00	16:26:00	16:19:00	16:24:00	5	10	72.98	
1965	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	15:34:00	16:15:00	15:42:00	16:11:00	29	41	72.82	
1966	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	13:52:00	14:37:00	13:57:00	14:33:00	36	45	72.13	
1967	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	12:24:00	13:11:00	12:34:00	13:05:00	31	47	71.38	
1968	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	09:57:00	10:53:00	10:15:00	10:46:00	31	56	370.6	
1969	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	08:49:00	09:28:00	08:56:00	09:24:00	28	39	69.67	
1970	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	07:51:00	08:28:00	07:58:00	08:26:00	28	37	69.02	
1971	27.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	7	06:58:00	08:17:00	07:11:00	08:12:00	61	79	368.4	
1972	28.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	15:01:00	15:40:00	15:08:00	15:38:00	30	39	75.78	
1973	28.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	3	14:56:00	15:43:00	15:06:00	15:39:00	33	47	75.13	
1974	28.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	13:29:00	13:56:00	13:34:00	13:54:00	20	27	74.35	
1975	28.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	12:22:00	13:01:00	12:30:00	12:55:00	25	39	373.9	
1976	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	17:11:00	17:46:00	17:16:00	17:40:00	24	35	82.58	
1977	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	14:37:00	15:32:00	14:40:00	15:29:00	49	55	1382	
1978	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	11:22:00	11:54:00	11:27:00	11:48:00	21	32	81.08	
1979	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	4	10:05:00	10:42:00	10:12:00	10:38:00	26	37	80.55	
1980	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	09:44:00	10:02:00	09:49:00	09:57:00	8	18	79.93	
1981	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	09:23:00	09:58:00	09:25:00	09:56:00	31	35	79.63	
1982	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	2	09:07:00	09:47:00	09:19:00	09:44:00	25	40	79.05	
1983	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	2	09:07:00	09:32:00	09:09:00	09:29:00	20	25	78.38	
1984	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	08:54:00	09:31:00	09:00:00	09:28:00	28	37	77.97	
1985	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	1	06:44:00	07:08:00	06:45:00	07:04:00	19	24	77.35	
1986	29.07.2021	HB-		LS	LS	2	06:34:00	07:17:00	06:42:00	07:14:00	32	43	76.95	

Figure 4. Excerpt from electric flight data records (Sensitive Data Censored).

2.3. Semi-Structured Interviews

In order to gain a broad overview of current trends and developments as well as the experiences and opinions of key stakeholders in the electric GA ecosystem, we conducted an array of 21 interviews (eight were survey-related follow-up interviews) and exchanges between October 2024 and November 2024, mostly via video and telephone calls (between 30 and 60 min) (listed in Table 1).

Table 1. Interview overview.

ID	Year-Month	Region	Role
1	October 2024	Australia	eViation Charging Solutions Developer
2	October 2024	Spain	Flight School
3	October 2024	Germany	Electric Aircraft Sales
4	October 2024	France	Flight School
5	November 2024	Netherlands	eViation Charging Infrastructure Developer
6	November 2024	France	Aircraft Leasing
7	November 2024	Switzerland	Airport Management
8	November 2024	France	Aeroclub
9	November 2024	Switzerland	Flight School
10	November 2024	Slovenia	Aircraft Manufacturer
11	November 2024	Switzerland	Private Pilot
12	November 2024	Switzerland	Private Pilot
13	November 2024	Switzerland	Private Pilot
14	November 2024	Switzerland	Private Pilot
15	November 2024	Switzerland	Airport Management
16	November 2024	Switzerland	Airfield and Flight School
17	November 2024	United Kingdom	Charging Infrastructure
18	November 2024	Switzerland	Flight Instructor
19	November 2024	Switzerland	Airfield Manager
20	November 2024	Switzerland	Flying Club
21	November 2024	Switzerland	Student Pilot

The participants were recruited via a combination of convenience and snowball sampling. In the early phase, the interviewees were recruited based on previous online research with the goal to find relevant experts and key stakeholders. We reached out to the experts via various communication channels such as e-mail, phone calls, and LinkedIn messages.

The complementary snowball sampling method enabled us to recruit further interviewees through the personal networks of preceding interviewees who recommended further candidates. The candidates were based in Switzerland, France, Spain, Germany, the Netherlands, Australia, Slovenia, and the United Kingdom. These countries are currently key players in the light electric aircraft and plane charging sectors.

The interviewees represented a diverse range of stakeholders: from the fields of charging solutions and infrastructure development, electric aircraft sales and manufacturing, and airport management and from aircraft leasing/sales, flight schools and clubs. It must be noted that nine participants were based in Switzerland, reflecting the study's regional focus.

Where permission to record the call was granted by the survey participants, the interviews were recorded and transcribed using automated transcription tools. As these tools tend to make many mistakes, especially when the language is very technical, interviewees are not native speakers of the interview language, or when the internet connection is bad, etc., the transcripts were then manually reviewed and edited for accuracy.

To analyze the interview data, we employed the qualitative data analysis software ATLAS.ti v24. An exploratory thematic analysis was conducted to identify key themes

emerging from the interviews. The coding process was conducted in a hybrid fashion, i.e., guided both by predefined themes from the semi-structured interview guide and by emergent themes discovered during the analysis.

This approach allowed us to systematically extract insights related to infrastructure challenges, charging standardization, policy implications, and stakeholder perspectives on eViation adoption. Themes that were deemed highly important to the study were further investigated and striking quotes selected for implementation in the results section of this paper. In cases where recording of interviews was not possible, written notes were taken, and key points were integrated into the thematic analysis framework to ensure consistency across all interviews.

2.4. Quantitative Online Survey

To understand the experiences, opinions, and needs of the Swiss GA and flight school community, we conducted an online survey informed by a literature analysis, expert interviews, and data-driven insights from the flight record analysis. The survey primarily targeted managers of flight schools, flying clubs, and airfields but also included flight instructors, private pilots, and student pilots through the use of filter questions. The survey included three main categories of questions:

1. **Demographic Information:** Questions covered gender, age, education level, and roles within GA (e.g., private pilot, flight instructor, airfield manager).
2. **eViation Experience:** Respondents were asked about their familiarity with and experience in flying electric aircraft, including types of aircraft flown, flight hours, and first exposure to eViation.
3. **Infrastructure Needs and Preferences:** This section explored perceptions of current charging infrastructure, preferences for charging standards, interest in multimodal charging solutions, and barriers to adopting eViation.

The survey utilized a mix of closed-ended, multiple-choice, and open-ended questions, designed to capture both quantitative data (e.g., ranking barriers by significance) and qualitative insights (e.g., written feedback on infrastructure gaps). The survey was trilingual (German, French, and English) to ensure inclusivity and reach across Switzerland's linguistic regions.

Pilot testing with a small group of researchers and GA stakeholders along with an iterative improvement of the questionnaire ensured clarity and validity before the survey was launched. A full structural overview of the survey is summarized in Appendix A.

Administered via the software *Unipark* (www.unipark.de), the survey was distributed to the heads of flight schools and airfields (obtained as a public list from FOCA), as well as via AlpinAirPlanes GmbH to their Pipistrel Velis Electro lessees on 25 October 2024. The managers and administrators were kindly asked to also distribute the survey link internally within their flight clubs and flight schools to reach flight instructors, private pilots, and student pilots. A purposive sampling approach was employed, ensuring responses from key stakeholders in the sector.

The survey garnered 69 responses by 3 December 2024. Of these, 64% (44 respondents) fully completed the survey, while 36% (25 respondents) partially completed it. The respondent demographic was predominantly male (98%, $n = 43$) with an average age of 52.9 years ($SD = 14.8$) and a median age of 54 years. Educationally, 82% ($n = 36$) held higher or tertiary education degrees, and the survey was primarily conducted in German (82%, $n = 36$), followed by French (16%, $n = 7$) and English (2%, $n = 1$).

Participants held multiple roles within GA: 64% were private pilots ($n = 28$), 18% student pilots ($n = 8$), 46% flight instructors ($n = 20$), 41% involved in managing flight schools ($n = 18$), 25% managing flight clubs ($n = 11$), and 9% managing airfields

(n = 4), with 7% engaged in other roles such as theory instructors or aviation consultants (n = 3).

It must be noted that multiple roles could be selected by participants. Regarding electric flight experience, 64% (n = 28) had eViation flying experience (foremost Pipistrel Velis/Alpha Electro, but also other types such as *Elektra Trainer*, or *Bristell B23*), with flight hours ranging from less than two hours to over two hundred electric flight hours. The first electric flight among participants occurred predominantly between 2020 and 2024, indicating a recent uptick in eViation adoption due to the advent of the Pipistrel Velis Electro.

This demographic and experiential profiling of the survey respondents provides valuable context for analyzing the current state and needs of the Swiss GA community, particularly in relation to the integration of eViation technologies. For a detailed breakdown of the survey sample, please refer to Table 2.

Table 2. Survey sample overview.

Category	n/Value	%
Total Sample	69	100%
Partially Completed Surveys	25	36%
Fully Completed Surveys	44	64%
Demographics		
Gender		
Male	43	98%
Female	1	2%
Age		
Mean (Std. Dev.)	52.9 (14.8)	/
Median	54	/
Min	20	/
Max	80	/
Education		
Higher Education/Tertiary Education	36	82%
Secondary Education/Vocational Training	8	18%
(Survey) Language		
German	36	82%
French	7	16%
English	1	2%
Role in General Aviation (Multiple Roles Possible)		
Private Pilot	28	64%
Student Pilot	8	18%
Flight Instructor	20	46%
Management of Flight School	18	41%
Management of Flight Club	11	25%
Management of Airfield	4	9%
Other (Theory Instructor, Aviation Consultant)	3	7%
Electric Flight Experience		
Yes, Has Experience	28	64%
<2 h (e.g., introductory flight)		
2–5 h	4	9%
6–10 h	1	2%
11–15 h	3	7%
16–20 h	5	11%
21–30 h	4	9%
31–40 h	2	5%
41–50 h	2	5%
51–100 h	3	7%

Table 2. *Cont.*

Category	n/Value	%
101–200 h	3	7%
201–300 h	1	2%
First Electric Flight		
2024	6	14%
2023	7	16%
2022	5	11%
2021	3	7%
2020	3	7%
2019	2	5%
2016	1	2%
before 2015	1	2%

Survey responses were exported to SPSS .sav and CSV files and then cleaned, preprocessed and analyzed using descriptive statistics, including measures of central tendency (means, medians) and dispersion (standard deviations, ranges), to summarize responses across key variables. Frequency distributions were examined to identify trends in stakeholder perspectives. After a few attempts of conducting valid inferential statistical tests on our data, it was decided to keep the analysis at a descriptive level due to the relatively small response sample size.

Open-ended survey responses were analyzed using qualitative content analysis, where responses were systematically coded and categorized into key themes. Recurring patterns in qualitative feedback were identified to complement quantitative findings and provide deeper insights into stakeholder perspectives on infrastructure needs, policy measures, and technological challenges.

The statistical analysis and data visualization were predominantly conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 29, Tableau (2024.2.4), Excel, and Python (3.13.1).

2.5. Limitations and Ethical Considerations

The study's findings are subject to several limitations. The survey sample (total $N = 69$, net sample: $n = 44$), including a notable number of partially completed responses, limits the generalizability of results. The purposive and snowball sampling strategies used for the qualitative interviews may also have introduced selection bias, potentially over-representing perspectives from certain stakeholder groups. Methodologically, our reliance on descriptive statistical analysis (due to sample size constraints) limits the robustness of inferential conclusions. Finally, administering the survey in three languages (German, French, and English) could have introduced translation or interpretation biases, potentially affecting response consistency.

For ethical research compliance, informed consent was obtained from all participants, and they were made aware of their right to withdraw at any time. Data from surveys, interviews, and flight records were anonymized to protect participant privacy, with identifying details removed or aggregated.

3. Results

This section is dedicated to summarizing key research results, beginning with an outline of noteworthy eViation charging network initiatives in Europe, followed by the analysis of eViation flight records and findings from the stakeholder survey as well as the semi-structured interviews.

3.1. Charging Networks and Initiatives in Europe

The development of charging networks for eViation in Europe is in its initial stages, with several noteworthy initiatives emerging. Our research highlights three international examples:

In France, TotalEnergies, in collaboration with Groupe ADP and the Fédération Française Aéronautique (FFA), has initiated the installation of electric aircraft charging stations at three airfields, i.e., Toussus-le-Noble, Étampes, and Pontoise, in the Île-de-France region [44]. These stations enable light electric aircraft to recharge within approximately one hour, supporting the decarbonization of aviation and reducing noise pollution at these sites.

In the Netherlands, NRG2fly is spearheading the development of a nationwide charging network for electric aircraft. The initiative aims to equip regional airports with charging infrastructure powered by locally generated renewable energy [45]. By establishing a standardized and interoperable charging system, NRG2fly seeks to facilitate sustainable e-flying between over 3000 locations across Europe [46]. As of November 2024, the network is preparing for a comprehensive European expansion, enabling point-to-point electric flights.

In the United Kingdom, AeroVolt has launched the world's first smart charging network for electric aircraft [47]. As of December 2024, AeroVolt has installed charging stations at seven sites, including Bournemouth, Lydd, Dunkeswell, and Shoreham airports, with plans to bring 12 more online soon. The company aims to expand to 24 sites by 2025 and over 60 in the long term [47]. AeroVolt's chargers are integrated into Octopus Energy's Electroverse network, allowing pilots to locate and access charging points easily. The initial chargers have a rated output of 22 kW, with plans to install 44 kW and 120 kW chargers in the near future to accommodate a wider range of electric aircraft [47,48]. A promising indication of future collaborations between charging network developers and aircraft manufacturers is the recent Memorandum of Understanding announced on 23 January 2025, between Sion-based H55 and AeroVolt [49]. This partnership highlights the growing synergy within the industry, paving the way for advancements in electric aviation infrastructure.

A project in Switzerland, by the Swiss Pipistrel distributor *AlpinAirPlanes GmbH*, operates the *E-Grid*, a network of eleven charging bases (22 kW) across Switzerland (see Figure 5), namely Gruyères (LSGT), Ecuwillens (LSGE), Schänis (LSZX), Grenchen (LSZG), Bern (LSZB)*, St. Gallen-Altenrhein (LSZR)*, Lausanne-Blécherette (LSGL), Kägiswil (LSPG), Lugano-Agno (LSZA), Raron (LSTA), and Môtiers (LSMI) (locations marked with "*" do not have the Pipistrel charger, but the compatible Eaton Green Motion 22 kW charger) [50]. The E-Grid supports regional and training operations, collaborating with local airfields and flight schools to promote eViation.

3.2. Flight Statistics

The fleet usage varies quite a lot between the different airfields and flight schools. In our case, one flight school in eastern Switzerland (one Pipistrel Velis Electro in their fleet) generates more than one-quarter of electric flight movements. The top five most active flight schools generate more than two-thirds of electric flight movements in Switzerland. In Figures 6 and 7, two trends become visible, namely that (a) the overall number of flights and airborne time have seen a slight decrease over time and (b) the flight movements follow a highly seasonal pattern, normal for visual flight rules (VFRs) operations as weather conditions become more adverse in fall and winter and usable daylight is significantly less, compared to spring and summer.

Figure 5. Current charging locations of E-Grid project as of December 2024 [50].

Figure 6. Electric flight movements and airborne time in Switzerland from 2021 to 2024. * stands for incomplete months /not data for the whole month available.

As can be seen in Figures 8 and 9, the vast majority of flights are local flights starting and ending at the same airport. While circuit training and local flights during PPL training are not uncommon, there is a low ratio of external landing points related to the shortcoming of the current charging infrastructure at Swiss airfields, both in terms of density and charging speeds.

3.3. Survey Results

We investigated the motivations of flight instructors and (former) student pilots. The results in Figure 10 show that environmental friendliness, noise reduction, and curiosity about innovation are strong motivators for both student pilots and flight instructors. However, instructors are uniquely motivated by the desire of students and the reduction in air pollutants, while students are driven by personal interest in sustainability and the positive public image of electric airplanes. Noise reduction stands out as the top motivator for instructors, reflecting its practical benefits, whereas students are slightly more driven by technological innovation.

Figure 7. Developments of block times, airborne times, and landings per flight.

Comparison of Local and Non-Local Flights (Overall and Per Year)

Figure 8. Ratio of local flights and flights with external landings (Pipistrel Velis E Fleet in Switzerland).

Analyzing key obstacles to operating and adopting electric aircraft in flying schools and clubs, the results shown in Figure 11 as well as Figure 12 reveal that the endurance of the electric plane and insufficient charging infrastructure at other airfields are perceived as the most significant challenges, highlighting critical operational issues related to range and charging accessibility during cross-country flights. Moderate concerns include charging speed, battery lifespan, and acquisition costs, pointing to the need for technological advancements and financial support to improve adoption. Likewise, operating costs and maintenance effort are less significant barriers, reflecting the expected cost advantages of

electric aircraft compared to conventional single-engine piston planes. Especially, the relatively low scores for lack of interest from flight instructors and student pilots are good signs and suggest that there may be enough momentum to keep the eViation transition going.

Figure 9. Most frequent airfield take-off and landing combinations with Pipistrel Velis Electro. Line thickness is indicative of frequency.

Figure 10. Motivations of CFIs (n = 7) and (former) student pilots (n = 19) to use electric planes in pilot training. S.E. in parentheses.

Figure 11. Perceived obstacles pertaining to operation of electric aircraft in flight schools/clubs (n = 26).

Satisfaction with eViation and Interest in Selected Sustainable Technologies

Figure 12. Interest in sustainable technologies (n = 44) and satisfaction with eViation (n = 28).

To overcome the main obstacles, it will be essential to focus on improving charging infrastructure, range, and technology while capitalizing on increasing stakeholder interest through education and targeted outreach.

As is depicted in Figure 13, only a third of the participants selected that they have a strong or very strong interest in faster charging infrastructure at their airfields, just as only about a third of the participants expressed that their interest in electric GA would increase strongly or very strongly if the charging speed of the current Pipistrel Velis Electro would be reduced by 50%.

Since EVs enjoyed, or even still enjoy, usage privileges and subsidization in many regions in the world, we were interested in whether this was the case for eViation in Switzerland, as well as what the community’s desires and opinions are. In the survey, 30% (n = 13) of participants stated that operational privileges had already been instated

at their home bases, with the most commonly stated privilege being (1) reduced hourly rates in training flights, (2) discounted landing fees and (3) discounted charter fees, as well as (4) permission for takeoffs/landings on days (e.g., Sundays, legal holidays) when fossil-fuel-powered planes are not allowed to take off/land (due to noise pollution).

Figure 13. Participants' interest in fast-charging and potential increase in interest in eViation if fast-charging would be available (n = 44).

Among those with existing privileges, 43% expressed interest in obtaining additional benefits. Six respondents provided detailed suggestions via an open-text field. One participant remarked, "All privileges that are possible" (German: "Alle Privilegien, die möglich sind") and additional suggestions included the following:

- Extended takeoff and landing time windows;
- More charging stations;
- Reduced landing fees;
- General fee reductions (e.g., free charging and half-price landing fees).

More than half (53%) of the participants stating that they had no operational privileges at their home bases expressed that they would like to have some introduced, with leading wishes being reduced landing fees and hourly rates in training, as well as permission for training flights and take-offs/landings at certain times of the day (e.g., lunchtime/noon) or on holidays or Sundays, which can be seen in Figure 14.

The one respondent that also picked the option "other, namely:" specified his wish to be "more and compatible charging infrastructure" (German: "mehr und kompatible Ladeinfrastruktur"), underlining previously identified insufficiencies pertaining to eViation charging infrastructure.

As we reasoned that fast-charging infrastructure especially at rural and regional airfields would make sense, we asked the survey participants whether they would support the idea of having a charging infrastructure for both planes and cars at the same time once the CCS charging standard would prevail. Surprisingly, out of the 38 participants who responded to this question, 42% were against this idea and 29% were not able to assess whether it would be useful.

Pilots' Wishlist of Additional Operational Privileges for eViation

Figure 14. Desired additional operational privileges for eViation (n = 16).

Regarding the preferred charging standard, the results were rather surprising, showing that the most selected answer was to have no preference, followed by Type 2 (AC), and then CCS. The GB/T connector, which is currently the standard connector used for the Pipistrel Velis Electro, was not selected at all (see Figure 15).

Charging Standard Preferences

Figure 15. Participants' charging standard preferences (single selection only, n = 12).

Regarding payment methods for charging at Swiss airfields, the respondents expressed a clear preference for credit/debit card payment options, followed by Twint (a Swiss digital payment application), and thirdly other smartphone apps (see Figure 16).

Towards the end of the questionnaire, we asked participants whether they would be interested in a potential pilot project featuring eViation fast-charging infrastructure at their home airfields. As shown in Figure 17, the most common response was "yes" (42%), while one-third of respondents (33%) explicitly indicated no interest. Approximately a quarter (24%) remained undecided, selecting "maybe".

Figure 16. Preferences for payment methods at plane charging stations (n = 38, multiple selections possible).

Figure 17. Respondents' interest in a potential eViation fast-charging infrastructure pilot project at their home bases (n = 44).

Geographically, strong support was observed mainly in German-speaking regions of Switzerland, with Raron (LSER) in Valais standing out as an exception. The least support came from the western and southern parts of the country. It should be noted that responses from the same airfield were not always consistent. In such cases, the mapped response reflects the highest-ranking participant's answer (e.g., if a private pilot from LSXY selected "maybe" while the airfield manager chose "yes", the airfield was mapped as "yes").

3.4. Interview Results

The following subsections summarize key themes and insights from our qualitative analysis of the semi-structured interviews.

3.4.1. Charging Infrastructure and Charging Speeds

During the interviews, the interviewees' answers varied quite a lot regarding the need for faster charging and satisfaction levels with the current charging speed of the Pipistrel Velis Electro. To our surprise, many interviewees expressed that they are satisfied with the current charging time of the Velis Electro using the manufacturer's own standard 22 kW charger.

Interviewee 2, for example, explained "charging from 35–40% to 95% takes 40 min or less. For our standard use, charging speed is not such a problem" yet remarked "if we use it more intensively, it will be a problem". He also added "some flight instructors here say it's unfeasible. They don't want to teach electric because they want to have multiple students".

On the other hand, Interviewee 4 highlighted "the charging time (. . .) is not a challenge for us today. During that time, students are debriefing with the instructor". Likewise, a private pilot from a small airfield in Switzerland underlined "if you take a break of about an hour, the plane is usually back at 95%. For the operations we do, charging speed has never been a major issue".

Nevertheless, the Dutch charging infrastructure developer, Interviewee 5, uttered his concerns regarding the future proofness of current 22 kW chargers: "With the current chargers, we're limited to certain speeds, and the lack of faster chargers is holding back the full potential of electric operations".

3.4.2. Charging Standardization

During the exchanges and interviews, most people who were asked signaled their support for the idea of charging infrastructure standardization, especially towards versatile CCS standard-based chargers, widely common in the automotive sector, especially in Europe. While this was the tenor during our talks and interviews, our survey results do not mirror this, as most participants stated to have no preference for a charging standard (see [Figure 15]).

Given that more electric plane manufacturers will soon enter the market with their models, the GA industry must facilitate concerted efforts to build non-proprietary and open, even multimodal, charging infrastructure. Interviewee 11 highlighted "it would be absolutely inefficient to have individual charging devices set up everywhere. This would be a waste of material. A standardized infrastructure is what's needed at regional airports to make the investment worthwhile". Similarly, Interviewee 5 stressed "(. . .) it's essential to have one universal standard for the future".

3.4.3. Grid Constraints at Airfields

Most of our interview partners were fond of the idea of implementing faster charging infrastructure for the Pipistrel Velis Electro and forthcoming plane models. However, many pointed out that especially at smaller and rural airfields, this idea faces significant grid and power constraints that challenge the scalability of eViation. Stakeholders consistently pointed out limited grid capacity at smaller airfields, making it difficult to support high-powered chargers.

As Interviewee 4 noted, "the electricity line and the power are not sufficient to support a 22 kW or even 44 kW charging device". Solutions like solar-powered stations and micro-grids have been suggested to overcome these limitations, enabling airfields to operate more independently of national grids. A stakeholder from the Netherlands emphasized their

issue of grid congestion: “Our grid is sort of stuck. (...) If you want to add a lot of energy capacity at a business park or an airport, it would be wise to set up an independent micro-grid with PV solutions, wind turbines, or a gas turbine, so you can work independently from the national grid”.

These insights highlight the challenges involved in developing faster eViation charging infrastructure as well as underline the critical need for investments in energy infrastructure to enable the widespread adoption of eViation.

3.4.4. eViation as a Means of Environmental Justification

Throughout several interviews, interviewees from the categories of private pilots and student pilots mentioned to have experienced pressure and negative comments from their acquaintances and colleagues pertaining to the negative environmental impacts associated with their leisure-based flying activities. Many confirmed that flying electrically is not only a more sustainable way for them to fly but also helps reducing such comments and external pressure.

For instance, Interviewee 12 said “I fly [here] because I can fly electrically. This fits much better with my philosophy, and I no longer have to justify myself for my passion”.

A French private pilot (Interviewee 8) argued “the idea is not just to have an electric plane but to show that we care about our surroundings. It’s not just about flying; it’s about doing it responsibly”.

A flight instructor from Spain stressed that “we must make this trip to sustainable aviation. Whatever we like or not, whatever we want, it’s the way to continue flying and justify our activity”.

Overlapping with findings from previous research [3], for some, the electric flight option is not only a justification towards others but also a reason for them keep flying or even have started PPL(A) training in the first place.

3.4.5. Government Support for Charging Infrastructure and Electric Planes

In exchange with several international stakeholders attempting to establish strategic aircraft charging networks at airfields in their own or even other countries, two points were prominently mentioned.

Firstly, the necessity of and wish for increased government support were emphasized by all key stakeholders. Secondly, except for our Dutch interviewee, all others expressed a high degree of frustration with government responses when asking for monetary support to establish better charging infrastructure. In the Netherlands, Interviewee 5 explained “usually subsidies cover about 50% of the cost. The rest you need to invest yourself or find private investors. (...) This shared cost model is typical, but it limits how quickly we can grow”.

Our U.K. respondent explained that the way to go forward at this point is to rely on private investors’ funding and aim for larger GA markets outside of Europe, primarily the North American market. Exchange with German eViation pioneers also led to reports of frustration with lacking support from state and national governments.

Similarly, in Switzerland, several stakeholders explained that they had already sought funding from various public funding bodies over recent years, yet remained without success. In France, two streams of government support were mentioned. A president of a small aeroclub in France explained that their club receives small subsidies from the local municipality and remarked “For me, subsidies are essential. Locally, the city gives some money, like €5000, which is a good start. But I need to continue applying at the departmental and regional levels to support the transition to quieter and greener electric aircraft”.

Other respondents emphasized the partnership of *TotalEnergies* and French airfields to establish a dense charging network. Nevertheless, some respondents from outside of France also mentioned this partnership yet expressed doubts over the true intentions of *TotalEnergies* and the implementation timeline of a charging network since the fossil-fuel dominant company is also a key supplier of AVGAS100LL.

3.4.6. Waiting for Technological Improvement

While many interviewees expressed that the Pipistrel Velis Electro already satisfies their needs for basic pilot training or even for short private flights, there were several interviewees indicating that they are looking forward to and waiting for battery upgrades to extend the feasible endurance and range, as well as some indicating that they are waiting for completely new models with a particular frequent mention of the electric B23 by H55.

At the same time, many mentioned that a barrier to adoption or rather further adoption of electric aircraft technology is the infrastructure for charging, both in terms of coverage as well as charging speeds. Concerns about range/battery capacity, charging times and charging infrastructure density are well-documented barriers to adoption of EVs (see for instance, Pamidimukkala, Kermanshachi, Rosenberger and Hladik [31], Pamidimukkala et al. [51], Powell et al. [52]).

Interviewee 4 explained “we are really waiting for one hour and a half to make the circuit between airfields. But what we miss now is the airplane as well as the network of charging stations”.

4. Discussion

This study demonstrates that the adoption of eViation in the GA context is influenced by a complex interplay of infrastructural, technological, and policy-related factors. Our findings align with previous research on the barriers to electric mobility, particularly those faced by early adopters of electric vehicles (EVs) [38,51]. These parallels highlight that targeted investments and coordinated stakeholder actions are necessary to overcome challenges such as insufficient charging infrastructure, range limitations, and financial constraints.

The survey results revealed that while stakeholders recognize the environmental and operational benefits of eViation, including reduced noise as well as carbon and health-adverse lead and bromide emissions, the lack of standardized charging infrastructure poses a significant barrier. This finding supports the conclusions of Dubois [19], who emphasized that the absence of interoperable charging systems limits the scalability of eViation. The current reliance on the proprietary GB/T charging system for Pipistrel Velis Electro aircraft further compounds this issue, stressing the urgency of adopting a universal charging standard, such as the Combined Charging System (CCS). In addition, the market size of electric light aircraft is rather small in Switzerland as well as other countries, posing an additional challenge to private investors and initiatives that would try to establish a profit-oriented charging network.

Stakeholder perspectives, gathered through interviews, revealed a prominent divergence in priorities. While many flight schools and private pilots reported moderate satisfaction with the current charging speeds for training and local flights, the limited density of chargers at airfields was consistently highlighted as a critical operational constraint. This aligns with the broader literature on electric mobility transitions, where the availability of charging infrastructure often outweighs incremental technological improvements [38,52].

The role of renewable energy integration emerged as a key opportunity to address grid constraints at smaller airfields, a challenge well-documented in the Pipistrel-oriented life cycle analysis study by Arvidsson, Nordelöf and Brynolf [18]. Solar-powered microgrids,

combined with battery storage systems, can enhance energy independence and operational resilience at rural locations, enabling them to support fast-charging infrastructure.

Additionally, this study found that societal and environmental pressures play a crucial role in motivating eViation adoption. Several stakeholders mentioned that flying electric aircraft reduced the external criticism they faced for engaging in leisure aviation, a finding that resonates with previous stakeholder perception evaluations [3,28].

The alignment of eViation with sustainability narratives not only enhances its appeal but also positions it as a solution to the negative public perceptions surrounding GA, sparking questions as to whether currently economically unviable investments in charging infrastructure would eventually have an overall positive economic impact on the GA sector since they might ensure the continued existence and permission of exercising GA flying activities at many airfields facing political pressure.

Finally, the survey and interview results highlight a “chicken-and-egg” dilemma, reminiscent of early EV adoption barriers. Without adequate charging infrastructure, demand for electric aircraft remains low; however, the development of such infrastructure requires sufficient market uptake to justify investment. Lessons from, for instance, Norway’s EV transition [30] suggest that combining infrastructure development with targeted incentives, such as reduced landing fees, training flight time privileges (e.g., flight training on holidays or during lunch hours) and subsidies, can create a mutually reinforcing cycle of adoption and infrastructure growth. However, one must keep in mind that the GA market is far from being as large as the automotive market, which is why it is even more important to catalyze infrastructure development with sufficient subsidies and targeted policies to facilitate a fast sustainability transition in GA.

5. Conclusions

This study explored the key factors influencing the feasibility of a fast-charging network for electric planes in Switzerland, focusing on stakeholder perceptions, infrastructure needs, and policy considerations. By integrating 7168 electric flight records, 69 survey responses (net sample $n = 44$), and 21 stakeholder interviews, the study provides empirical evidence on the primary barriers and opportunities shaping the transition to electric GA. This chapter shall conclude the study with a summary of our key findings and recommendations.

Key Findings

- While battery endurance (Mean: 4.35, SD: 0.32) was ranked the most important issue in current eViation, the main barrier to eViation adoption, not related to the electric planes themselves, is charging infrastructure density: Survey results indicate that insufficient charging infrastructure at airfields was rated as one of the top obstacles (mean importance rating: 4.12, SD: 0.27). The flight record analysis further supports this, showing that 84% of flights remained local due to insufficient charging infrastructure at destination airfields.
- Charging speed is currently only a moderate concern: Survey responses suggest that charging speed had a mean importance rating of 3.46 (SD: 0.32), indicating moderate concern among users. Additionally, neutral to high satisfaction levels were reported regarding charging speeds, suggesting that some users are comfortable with current technology while others seek faster solutions. There may be, however, a certain bias in those ratings, since, currently, eViation users could be still seen as early adopters and enthusiasts that may accept the drawback of long charging times compared to regular AVGAS refueling. Our qualitative interviews were in line with the results.

- Standardization is essential: Charging standard preferences indicate that 58.3% of survey respondents had no preference, but among those who did, Type 2 (AC) was preferred by 25% and CCS by 16.7%. While the survey responses yielded only a little insight into charging standard and connector preferences of GA community, the interviews consistently did. This indicates the need for clear industry standardization efforts to ensure interoperability. Both survey responses and interview data, with only few exceptions, highlight a preference for transitioning from the GB/T standard to CCS, which aligns with emerging industry trends, especially with the EV sector in Europe and North America.
- Operational constraints due to battery limitations: The highest-rated obstacle in the study was aircraft endurance limitations (mean importance rating: 4.35, SD: 0.32), confirming that current battery technology does not yet support full PPL(A) syllabus training, which is in line with many aforementioned studies on eViation in flight training [9,19,28,53,54]. Our flight record analysis shows an overall average airborne time of 25 min per flight, with an average block time of 35 min. This limitation necessitates hybrid training models combining electric and piston-engine aircraft.
- Policy measures could catalyze adoption: Based on expert interviews, financial incentives, landing fee discounts and grid-capacity investments were identified as critical enablers for increasing eViation adoption. The survey showed that the GA community widely supports subsidies and operational privileges in the context of eViation.
- Environmental and public perception benefits: Many pilots, flight instructors and administrators reported that flying electric aircraft helps reduce public criticism of GA flying activities, suggesting a broader societal benefit beyond carbon reduction, effectively mitigating the risk of airfield closures or further restrictions being placed on recreational flying and flight training activities at airfields.

Recommendations

- Grid Infrastructure Upgrades: Many regional and rural airfields currently lack the necessary grid capacity to support fast-charging infrastructure. The installation of higher-capacity transformers and grid reinforcements would be required to accommodate high-power charging. However, these upgrades are costly and require long-term planning in coordination with local utilities and regulatory bodies. Financial support mechanisms, such as subsidies or co-financed grid expansion programs, should be considered to address this infrastructural bottleneck and accelerate the adoption of eViation.
- Expand charging network density at strategic airfields, prioritizing flight training hubs.
- Increase charger power levels to support 50 kW + fast-charging for operational flexibility and potential intermodal usage, i.e., for planes and cars/ground vehicles.
- Implement standardized CCS chargers to ensure long-term compatibility across different electric aircraft models. Whenever possible, charging infrastructure should be designed for multimodal use and located in strategic places at airfields, allowing for both electric aircraft and ground vehicles (such as cars and service vehicles) to share compatible fast-charging solutions and increase overall utilization of charging infrastructure and thus economic viability.
- Introduce policy incentives such as subsidies, reduced landing fees and infrastructure co-financing to accelerate adoption.
- Leverage renewable energy solutions and battery storage (e.g., microgrids, solar panels) to address grid limitations at smaller airfields with low electric power availability.

The results contribute to the broader discourse on sustainable aviation by providing a roadmap for addressing infrastructure and adoption challenges in eViation. While they are focused on Switzerland, the findings offer valuable insights for other regions seeking to advance sustainable GA.

Future research should conduct a comprehensive feasibility assessment of a fast-charging network for eViation, incorporating economic modeling, cost-benefit-analysis, grid infrastructure evaluations, and policy simulations. Further studies should also ideally involve applied research and pilot projects for strategic eViation fast-charging infrastructure. Additionally, further studies should explore the long-term impacts of multimodal charging infrastructure, the economic viability of renewable energy integration, and the implications of technological advancements in electric aircraft.

By addressing the identified challenges and leveraging stakeholder momentum, Switzerland and other nations can position eViation as a cornerstone of their sustainable aviation strategies, fostering innovation, environmental stewardship, and societal acceptance in GA.

Funding: This research was funded by the Swiss Innovation Agency (Innosuisse), grant number 71427.1 INNO-EE. The APC was funded by the Open Access Fund of the University of Basel.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in this study.

Data Availability Statement: The raw data from surveys and interviews supporting the conclusions of this article can be made available in anonymized form by the authors on request. Restrictions apply to the availability of the flight records obtained from AlpinAirPlanes GmbH.

Acknowledgments: We would like to express our deep appreciation to AlpinAirPlanes GmbH for collaborating with this research project, including the distribution of the survey and providing access to their professional network of contacts, as well as providing flight data records. Furthermore, we want to thank the student assistant Leonid Wouters for his help with the project.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AVGAS 100LL	aviation gasoline (100 Octane Low-Lead)
CCS	Combined Charging System
CO _{2e}	Carbon Dioxide Equivalent
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EV	electric vehicle
eViation	electric aviation
FOCA	Federal Office of Civil Aviation (Switzerland)
GA	General Aviation
GB/T	guóbìāo/tuǐjiàn (“recommended/voluntary national standard”)
GHG	greenhouse gas
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
PPL(A)	private pilot license (Airplane)
SAF	Sustainable Aviation Fuel
VFRs	visual flight rules

Appendix A

Appendix A.1.

Table A1. Pipistrel Velis Electro key facts and specifications (based on: Pipistrel ¹ Aircraft, AOPA ², A4Aviation ³).

Category	Specification
General	
Aircraft Type	Fully electric, two-seat trainer
Manufacturer	Pipistrel Aircraft
Certification	EASA Type-Certified (June 2020) Type Certificate EASA.A.573
Role	Flight training, General Aviation
Noise Level	Significantly lower than combustion trainers
Dimensions	
Wingspan	10.71 m (35.1 ft)
Length	6.47 m (21.2 ft)
Height	2.28 m (7.48 ft)
Wing Area	9.51 m ² (102.4 ft ²)
Weight and Load	
Empty Weight	428 kg (944 lbs)
Maximum Takeoff Weight (MTOW)	600 kg (1323 lbs)
Useful Load	~172 kg (379 lbs)
Maximum Payload	~172 kg (including pilot, passenger, baggage)
Performance	
Cruise Speed (@ 35 kW)	~90 kt (167 km/h, 104 mph)
V _{NE} (Never Exceed Speed)	108 kt (200 km/h, 124 mph)
Stall Speed (Flaps Down)	45 kt (83 km/h, 52 mph)
Rate of Climb	~3.4 m/s (~670 ft/min) at MTOW
Glide Ratio	~13:1
Endurance	~50 min + VFR reserve (30 min)
Range	~108 km (~67 miles)
Propulsion System	
Motor	Pipistrel E-811 electric motor
Power Output	57.6 kW peak, 49 kW continuous
Propeller	Fixed-pitch, composite
Cooling System	Liquid-cooled motor
Battery System	
Battery Type	2 × Lithium-ion battery packs (Pipistrel PB345V124E-L)
Total Energy Capacity	24.8 kWh
Voltage	345 V
Charging Time (Full)	~2 h
Charging Time (80%)	~30–45 min with fast charger
Battery Weight	~70 kg per pack (140 kg total)
Landing Gear	
Configuration	Fixed tricycle gear
Braking System	Hydraulic disk brakes
Avionics	
Flight Display	Garmin avionics (glass cockpit)
Safety Features	Integrated Battery Management System (BMS)

¹ <https://www.pipistrel-aircraft.com/products/velis-electro/> (accessed on 12 February 2025). ² <https://www.aopa.org/go-fly/aircraft-and-ownership/aircraft-guide/aircraft/pipistrel-velis-electro> (accessed on 12 February 2025). ³ <https://www.a4aviation.com/pipistrel/entrainment/velis-electro> (accessed on 12 February 2025).

Appendix A.2.

Table A2. Survey structure and content.

Section	Question/Content	Variable Type	Response Options
Introduction and Participant Information	- Purpose of the survey and confidentiality statement.	Informational	Not applicable.
1. Participant Roles	- Roles in General Aviation (GA).	Nominal	Private pilot, student pilot, flight instructor, flight school manager, airfield manager, flying club manager, others (with open field for specification).
	- Organization or airfield affiliation.	Nominal	Open-ended text field.
2. Demographics	- Age of the participant.	Ratio	Numeric input (years).
	- Gender.	Nominal	Male, female, prefer not to say.
	- Education level.	Nominal	Secondary education, vocational training, higher education, tertiary education, others.
	- Primary language used in GA.	Nominal	German, French, English, other (with open field for specification).
3. Experience with eViation	- Have you flown electric aircraft (e.g., Pipistrel Velis Electro)?	Binary	Yes, No.
	- Total flight hours using electric aircraft.	Ratio	Open numeric field for hours (e.g., less than 2 h, 2–5 h, 6–10 h, etc.).
	- Type of operations using electric aircraft.	Nominal	Training flights, private flights, others (with open field for specification).
4. Perceptions of eViation	- Main motivations for using electric aircraft (multiple options possible).	Ordinal	Environmental benefits, noise reduction, innovation, cost savings, public perception, other (open field).
	- Perceived barriers to using electric aircraft (multiple options possible).	Ordinal	Range limitations, charging speed, infrastructure availability, cost, maintenance, lack of instructor interest, student interest, other (open field).
	- Satisfaction with the current state of eViation technology and infrastructure.	Ordinal	Likert scale (e.g., very satisfied to very dissatisfied).
5. Infrastructure Preferences	- Importance of fast-charging infrastructure at airfields.	Ordinal	Likert scale (e.g., very important to not important).
	- Preferred charging standards for electric aircraft.	Nominal	GB/T, CCS, Type 2 (AC), no preference.
	- Interest in multimodal charging (shared chargers for cars and planes).	Binary	Yes, No, Not sure.
	- Interest in renewable energy integration for chargers (e.g., solar panels).	Binary	Yes, No.
6. Future Outlook	- How do you perceive the adoption of eViation in the next 5–10 years?	Ordinal	Likert scale (e.g., significant growth, moderate growth, no growth).
	- Would you participate in pilot programs or trials for electric aviation infrastructure or aircraft?	Binary	Yes, No.
	- Open-ended feedback on what would encourage eViation adoption.	Text	Open text field.

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